

TRAUMA, POSTMEMORY, AND SYMBOLISM IN COLUM MCCANN'S "LET THE GREAT WORLD SPIN"

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ABSTRACT

*This article examines how Colum McCann's novel *Let the Great World Spin* functions as a mediator of traumatic experience transmitted across generations. Focusing on the representation of the Vietnam War and the symbolic centrality of Philippe Petit's tightrope walk between the Twin Towers, the study explores how individual and familial traumas are transformed into forms of collective and cultural memory. The analysis draws on Cathy Caruth's concepts of latency, repetition, and the belated nature of traumatic experience, as well as Marianne Hirsch's theory of postmemory, in particular her notion of affiliative postmemory and visual testimony.*

Introduction. Colum McCann's novel *Let the Great World Spin* (2009) has frequently been read as a literary response to the terrorist attacks of 11 September 2001, even though its narrated time is the 1970s. Set primarily in New York City on the day of Philippe Petit's famous tightrope walk between the Twin Towers, the novel intertwines multiple storylines, bringing together characters from different social classes, ethnic backgrounds, and personal histories. Their lives intersect around a single, visually arresting event: the figure of a man walking on a wire high above the city. Methodologically, the article draws on trauma theory, especially Cathy Caruth's understanding of latency, repetition, and belated response, and on Marianne Hirsch's concept of postmemory, including her distinction between familial and affiliative postmemory and her focus on visual testimony. Using these frameworks, the article argues that the novel's symbolic objects and visual artefacts function as triggers of postmemory, transforming individual and familial experience into collective forms of remembrance.

Theoretical framework. The theoretical basis of this study is formed by two related but distinct approaches to trauma and memory: Cathy Caruth's trauma theory and Marianne Hirsch's concept of postmemory. Both scholars emphasize the belated, mediated nature of traumatic experience and its reliance on narrative or visual forms for its transmission. Cathy Caruth conceptualizes trauma as an event that is not fully experienced or understood at the moment it occurs. (Caruth, 104) Instead, trauma is characterized by latency: it returns belatedly, in the form of intrusive images, flashbacks, or repetitive gestures that resist integration into a coherent narrative. The subject does not simply "remember" a traumatic event; rather, the event imposes itself again and again, often in indirect and displaced forms.

Marianne Hirsch's theory of postmemory complements Caruth's emphasis on latency by focusing on the intergenerational transmission of traumatic experience. Postmemory designates the relationship that the "generation after" bears to the personal, collective, and cultural trauma of those who came before. (Hirsch, 4-5) Crucially, this relationship is mediated: postmemory is formed not through direct experience but through stories, images, and material artefacts. Hirsch distinguishes between familial postmemory, grounded in actual kinship ties and family narratives, and affiliative postmemory, in which individuals or groups adopt traumatic histories that are not "theirs" in a biological or genealogical sense but become part of their ethical and cultural horizon.

Analysis. The following example and episode make it possible to see how the Vietnam War, even after its end, continued to be actively rejected and criticized by civilians and passed into an affiliative form of postmemory. In this episode Dennis, one of the central characters of the chapter "ETHERWEST," which depicts the lives of American programmers and hackers in the 1970s, is presented as the oldest member of the group, a man who has completed two tours of duty in Vietnam. This biography makes him the bearer not only of a personal, but also of a cultural traumatic experience. In the episode, the hackers, tapping the phone calls of New York residents, learn about the tightrope walker and follow his performance through these calls. A distinctive feature of Dennis within the group is that he is portrayed as more mature and serious, something shaped by his service in Vietnam. After the war, the novel notes that he "worn his OCCIDENTAL DEATH T-shirt ever since he came home from the war." (McCann, 133) This item of clothing may also have a symbolic character. The phrase "Western death" points to a critique of military policy and highlights an awareness of the futility of war among veterans and civilians alike. In addition, this phrase on the T-shirt can be interpreted as an example of what Caruth defines as a "belated response," when traumatic experience is not understood at the moment it is lived through, but returns later through visual signs, gestures, or recurring images. In this context, Dennis's T-shirt becomes a symbol not only of his individual experience, but also of a form of cultural protest that expresses dissent with military action. It also functions as a visual trigger of postmemory which, in Hirsch's terms, serves as a mechanism for transmitting traumatic experience from the personal to the collective level, transforming individual memory into a form of cultural heritage, that is, into an affiliative form. Thus, in Dennis's image the ideas of Hirsch and Caruth intersect: the idea that the memory of war is preserved and transmitted through a symbol that visually conveys the character's trauma and traumatic experience.

Thus it can be concluded that the events of the Vietnam War affected many of the novel's characters, both main and secondary. The analysis of the characters has shown that wartime experience illustrates such aspects of traumatic experience as latency, the cyclical nature of reliving trauma, and the belated response to trauma, in accordance with Cathy Caruth's theory. Furthermore, according to Marianne Hirsch's theory, photographs and material artifacts have the capacity to accumulate traumatic experience and transmit it. In addition, we can note a difference in the representation of trauma in women and men. In the novel, women are generally depicted as carriers and guardians of traumatic experience, which is expressed through mourning, as in the images of Claire and Gloria. The male characters are more emotionally restrained: for example, Solomon remains silent about his son's death, while

Dennis expresses protest more through actions than through emotions. The text also traces how familial postmemory develops into affiliative postmemory and becomes part of cultural heritage.

It is also very important to emphasize the historical context of the events of 11 September 2001. Although the events of the novel unfold in the 1970s, the work is indirectly connected with the 2001 tragedy. The tightrope walker's crossing between the Twin Towers, as noted earlier, serves as a linking metaphor that unites the characters' fates into a single picture, and the image of Philippe Petit and the World Trade Center towers becomes a symbol of the memory of the terrorist attacks. The events of 9/11 left a deep mark on the collective memory of the United States and are today regarded as a traumatic event with its own post-traumatic history. In this context, the figure of the tightrope walker and the towers in the novel acts as a symbolic trigger, that is, a reminder of an event that is not spoken about directly but insistently returns, creating a traumatic context at the level of symbols. Thus Petit's figure, moving between the towers, becomes an image of fragile balance between life and death, and his actions foreshadow the destruction that occurred decades later.

It is also important to note that in the work the author employs what Marianne Hirsch terms the visual testimony of postmemory. On page 237 of the novel, Colum McCann places a real photograph of Philippe Petit at the moment when he is in the middle of the cable between the Twin Towers. In the photograph, the acrobat's figure appears as a tiny black dot, surrounded by circling helicopters. According to Hirsch, such images not only record a historical moment but also become mediators of memory for those generations that were not direct witnesses to the events. After the terrorist attacks, the significance of this photograph is heightened, and it is transformed into an artifact of postmemory, preserving visual testimony of what was destroyed and at the same time transmitting this memory to new generations.

Conclusion. The analysis of Colum McCann's novel *Let the Great World Spin* has demonstrated how a literary text can function as a mediator of traumatic experience transmitted across generations. Drawing on Cathy Caruth's concepts of the latency and cyclical nature of trauma, as well as Marianne Hirsch's notion of affiliative postmemory, it has been shown that personal and familial experiences are transformed into forms of collective memory. Particular attention has been paid to symbolic objects and artefacts that function as triggers activating traumatic recollections. These elements become not only signs of loss, but also instruments for transmitting historical trauma.

List of used literature:

1. Lackey M. *Biofiction. An Introduction.* – New York and London: Routledge, 2022. – 185 p.
2. McCann, Colum. *Let the Great World Spin.* – New York: Random House, 2009. – 350 p.
3. Caruth, Cathy. *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narrative, and History.* – Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1996. – 156 p.
4. Flannery, E. *Internationalizing 9/11: Hope and Redemption in Nadeem Aslam's The Wasted Vigil (2008) and Colum McCann's Let the Great World Spin. (2009) // English: Journal of the English Association.* – 2013. – Vol. 62, № 238. – P. 294–315.
5. Hirsch, Marianne. *The Generation of Postmemory // Poetics Today.* – 2008. – Vol. 29, № 1. – P. 103–128.

6.Кузнецова, О. Теневая сторона эмпатии: взгляд на викарную травм. // Академия профессионального потенциала. – 2021

